

In-Plane Tensile Strength of Multidirectional Composite Laminates

R. Y. Kim

Research Institute, University of Dayton, 300 College Park Avenue, Dayton, OH 45469, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

A simple approach using quadratic failure theory has been employed to predict the in-plane tensile strength of multidirectional laminates as an engineering approximation. The experimental result obtained from various types of laminates of T300/5208 graphite/epoxy was found to be in good agreement with predictions except for those laminates revealing delamination.

INTRODUCTION

Most composite laminates for structural application consist of multidirectional layers to meet the structural integrity. Prediction of the in-plane strength of a multidirectional laminate is of great importance in design of the laminate as well as development of material systems. Most laminates reveal a progressive type of failure when subjected to an applied stress. The final failure of a laminate is usually followed by the weaker ply failure in the form of matrix cracking along fiber direction. In certain laminates delamination is also initiated at the free edges and propagated toward the middle of the test specimen. The type and degree of these damages vary widely depending upon lamination including stacking sequence, layer thickness, and material properties.

In view of this progressive failure process in multidirectional laminates, a variety of approaches have been reported to develop a reliable methodology to predict the in-plane tensile strength (1,2,3). These approaches are based on the damage caused by only transverse cracking and can be divided into two groups, depending upon complete elimination of damaged ply or employing damage functions in calculation of strength. Therefore, success of these approaches appears to remain in question until one has a proper understanding of the damage process and its influence on the strength change, including other failure modes such as delamination and fiber break, etc. Furthermore, one of the main obstacles in accepting these approaches in strength prediction is complexity in the calculation process with the uncertainty of gaining any improvement.

In this work a simple approach is employed to predict the in-plane tensile strength of a multidirectional laminate as an engineering approximation. To achieve this, we made an assumption that ultimate failure of multidirectional laminates occurs upon the strongest ply failure for a given externally-applied

stress resultant ignoring the damages incurred in the course of loading. The in-plane stress components in each constituent ply for a given laminate were calculated using laminated plate theory. The quadratic failure criterion developed by Tsai and Wu is then applied to the respective ply (4). The analytical results were compared with experimental results obtained from a variety of laminates including laminates showing delamination before final failure. The damage process, in terms of delamination and transverse crack, was experimentally observed for selected laminates; and its influence on final failure was briefly given.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE AND DATA ANALYSIS

Three basic families of laminates used in this work are $[0_2/\pm\theta]_S$, $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$, and $[0/90/\pm\theta]_S$, with $\theta = 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60, 75,$ and 90 degrees. The effect of delamination can be considered by comparing the results of the last two families of laminates, since interlaminar normal stress at the free edge region is tension in the $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ laminates and compression in the $[0/90/\pm\theta]_S$ laminates under applied uniaxial tensile loading. Thus, the $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ laminates are prone to delaminate under uniaxial tension.

The material system used in this study was T300/5208 graphite/epoxy supplied in the prepreg form by Narmco Corporation. Tensile coupons, 3/4" wide and 5" long in gage section, were prepared from the panels fabricated in an autoclave according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The fiber volume was 66% by volume and density was 1.6. The side edges of some specimens of several laminates were polished with 5 and 0.5 micron polishing powder in order to facilitate microscopic examination for assessing damages incurred during loading. The stress level at initiation of delamination was determined by acoustic emission. It was found that the rate of acoustic emission signal was rapidly increased with onset of delamination and virtually remained in the same level until final failure. Some specimens were unloaded after delamination to delineate the delamination area by x-ray. Some specimens were also instrumented with longitudinal and transverse strain gages in order to compare the stress-strain behavior predicted by laminated plate theory. All specimens were stored in a desiccator until being tested and then subjected to uniaxial tension using an MTS testing machine in the load control mode, with the loading rate corresponding to 16.7 to 33.4 m/m.s of the strain rate.

Following is a list of the ply properties and the strength of unidirectional laminate used in calculation.

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= 137.9 \text{ GPa} & E_y &= 9.7 \text{ GPa} \\ E_S &= 5.5 \text{ GPa} & \nu_{xy} &= 0.3 \text{ GPa} \\ X &= X' = 1,380 \text{ MPa} & S &= S' = 90 \text{ MPa} \\ Y &= 48 \text{ MPa} & Y' &= 192 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

where

- X, X' = tensile and compressive strength in the longitudinal direction;
- S, S' = positive and negative shear strength in the longitudinal direction;
and
- Y, Y' = tensile and compressive strength in the transverse direction.

Because of experimental difficulty in determination of longitudinal compressive strength, we assumed that the compressive strength equaled the tensile strength for the T300/5208 graphite/epoxy. These material strengths allow determination of all the strength parameters, F 's, except F_{xy} in the quadratic failure criterion given in equation (1).

$$F_{xx}^2 \sigma_x^2 + F_{yy}^2 \sigma_y^2 + 2F_{xy} \sigma_x \sigma_y + F_{ss}^2 \sigma_s^2 + F_x^2 \sigma_x + F_y^2 \sigma_y + F_s^2 \sigma_s = 1 \quad (1)$$

In view of the difficulty in experimental determination of the F_{xy} term, Tsai introduced the following relation (5).

$$F_{xy} = F_{xy}^* \sqrt{\frac{F_{xx} F_{yy}}{F_{xy}^2}} \quad (2)$$

F_{xy}^* , is bounded by a negative to positive unit to insure that the failure surface will intercept each stress axis. Tsai assigned negative 1/2 to the value of F_{xy}^* based on a generalization of the Von Mises yield criterion for isotropic material. Details can be found in reference (5).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Damage in the form of transverse cracks in each off-axis layer and delamination between interfaces was observed at the free edges of a typical specimen of $[0_2/\pm\theta]_S$, $[0/90/\pm\theta]_S$, and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ laminates under incremental step loading. Figures 1 to 3 show photomicrographs of the damage, along with the stress level at which it was taken. In the $[0_2/\pm\theta]_S$ laminate for $\theta \leq 45$, no transverse crack was found until the last loading step which was in the range of 92 to 98% of the ultimate strength. However, in both $[0_2/\pm 60]_S$ and $[0_2/\pm 75]_S$ laminates, transverse cracks occurred and most of these cracks were extended to the entire off-axis layers at subsequent loading as shown in Figure 1. As the load is further increased, additional cracks, which usually occurred near the previous cracks, were found in the $+\theta$ layer as indicated by the arrow in Figure 1(b). In the $[0/90/\pm\theta]_S$ and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ laminates, transverse cracks were found in the 90-degree layer for all laminates and in the $\pm\theta$ layer for $\theta \geq 45$. Most cracks in the $\pm\theta$ -degree layers were located at or near the tip of the 90-degree layer crack as shown in Figures 2 and 3. When θ is small, say less than 30 degrees, transverse cracks were hardly found in the $\pm\theta$ layers.

Figure 1. Photomicrographs Showing Transverse Crack Under Static Loading.

An extensive delamination has been observed in the $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ laminate for $\theta \leq 45$ as shown in Figure 2. No delamination has been observed in the $[0/\pm 60/90]_S$ and $[0/\pm 75/90]_S$ laminates in spite of the presence of interlaminar normal stress at the free edges, as predicted by theory in reference (6). The reason for this appears to be that the magnitude of the interlaminar stress is too small to induce delamination. The extent of delamination toward the middle of the specimen was obtained by x-ray and is shown in Figure 4. The stress level at the moment the picture was taken is also indicated.

$[0/\pm 10/90]_s$ 800 MPa
(a)

$[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ 440 MPa
(b)

Figure 2. Photomicrographs Showing Transverse Crack and Delamination for $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$ Under Static Loading.

$[0/90/\pm 10]_s$ 931 MPa
(a)

$[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ 552 MPa
(b)

Figure 3. Photomicrographs Showing Transverse Crack for $[0/90/\pm\theta]_s$ Under Static Loading.

The crack data observed in each test was reduced in terms of number of cracks per centimeter in the respective off-axis layer obtained from the total number of cracks divided by the measured length (12.7 cm). This quantity is referred to as crack density and listed in Table 1. The stress level, in terms of fraction of ultimate strength, is also indicated. Some specimens were broken before reaching the previous stress level. Although the data in Table 1 is obtained from one specimen, it indicates general trends of transverse cracking which vary widely depending upon lamination and thickness for a given layer.

Figure 4. X-ray Pictures Showing Delamination Under Static Loading: Dark Area Indicates Delamination.

Figures 5 and 6 show the in-plane elastic constants (longitudinal modulus and Poisson's ratio) for the laminates of $[0_2/\pm\theta]_s$, $[0/90/\pm\theta]_s$, and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$ as a function of angle θ . Solid lines represent calculated results obtained by laminated plate theory, and experimental results are indicated by triangles for the $[0_2/\pm\theta]_s$ laminate and circles for the combined data of the $[0/90/\pm\theta]_s$ and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$ laminates. Each data point represents a mean of two specimens. The experimental data are compared well with the prediction for all angles.

In order to examine damage influence on the overall strain behavior of the laminates, Figure 7 presents the entire stress-strain curves for the $[0/90/\pm\theta]_s$ and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$ laminates, which show more damage than the $[0_2/\pm\theta]_s$ laminate. The straight line represents the result of linear analysis, and solid and open circles represent experimental data for the $[0/90/\pm\theta]_s$ and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_s$ laminates, respectively. The ordinate of the last data point corresponds to the ultimate strength of the specimen. The experimental data indicate fairly linear stress-strain behavior until final failure in most cases with a few exceptions. Slight nonlinear strain behavior in the specimen of the $[0/\pm 30/90]_s$ laminate is mainly attributed to the delamination which was extended to the strain gage area. Delamination in the other laminates appears to be confined to near the free-edge region until final failure. This is based on the previous work, indicating that axial strain change only occurred when either delamination or transverse cracking develops in the gage area (7). The small amount of strain jumps at a higher stress level in the specimen of the $[0/90/\pm 60]_s$ and $[0/\pm 60/90]_s$ laminates is

TABLE 1
CRACK DENSITY

Laminate	Stress		Ply Orientation	Crack Density #/cm
	MPa	Fraction of Ultimate		
[0 ₂ /±60] _s	817	.95	+60	23.0
			-60/-60	12.5
[0 ₂ /±75] _s	758	.93	+75	22.3
			-75/-75	14.6
[0/90/±10] _s	931	1.02	90	3.7
			+10	0
			-10/-10	0
[0/±10/90] _s	800	1.01	+10	0
			-10	0
			90/90	20.4
[0/90/±15] _s	758	.96	90	0.4
			+15	0
			-15/-15	0
[0/±15/±90] _s	656	1.01	+15	0
			-15	0.2
			90/90	12.0
[0/90/±30] _s	715	1.00	90	6.5
			+30	0
			-30/-30	0
[0/±30/90] _s	489	.98	30	0
			-30	2.8
			90/90	13.6
[0/90/±45] _s	552	1.04	90	10.4
			+45	1.9
			-45/-45	0.1
[0/±45/90] _s	453	.91	+45	0.3
			-45	8.7
			90/90	10.8
[0/90/±60] _s	400	.84	90	21.5
			+60	21.3
			-60/-60	13.0
[0/±60/90] _s	474	.91	+60	9.1
			-60	14.3
			90/90	8.9
[0/90/±75] _s	441	.91	90	15.4
			+75	18.0
			-75/-75	12.0
[0/±75/90] _s	405	.96	+75	19.5
			-75	18.3
			90/90	13.1

attributed to the transverse cracks which occurred in the strain gage area. Similar jumps were observed in the laminates of $\theta = 75$. It remains in question at present how this small amount of the observed strain change will contribute to the final failure of the laminate.

Figure 5. Longitudinal Modulus Predicted by Laminated Plate Theory. Symbols represent experimental results.

Figure 6. Longitudinal Poisson's Ratio Predicted by Laminated Plate Theory. Symbols represent experimental results.

Figure 7. Stress-Strain Curves Predicted by Laminated Plate Theory. Solid and open circles represent experimental data.

Figures 8 and 9 show analytical prediction of the failure stress of the respective layers for the laminate family of $[0_2/\pm\theta]_S$, $[0/90/\pm\theta]_S$, and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ as a function of angle θ . The curing residual stresses are not included in this calculation. Various symbols in Figures 8 and 9 are experimental results which represent the mean of 10 to 11 specimens for a given laminate.

Figure 8. Comparison of Calculated In-Plane Tensile Strength with Experiment.

Figure 9. Comparison of Calculated In-Plane Tensile Strength with Experiment.

In the $[0_2/\pm\theta]_S$ laminate, the experimental results are fairly well compared with the analytical results of the 0-degree layer. Analysis gives a little conservative prediction in all cases except for $\theta = 10$ and 15 degrees. Analytical prediction shows almost identical strength for the 0-degree and off-axis layers up to approximately 30 degrees and, thereafter, the difference increases as increasing angle θ as shown in Figure 8. This implies that the laminates for $\theta \leq 30$ will fail without revealing progressive failure; that is, no off-axis ply failure will be preceded by final failure. On the other hand, off-axis ply failure will be anticipated before final failure when θ is greater than 30 degrees. The results of crack observation described earlier appear to support this analytical prediction except for the specimen of the $[0_2/\pm 45]_S$ laminate. Three more specimens of the $[0_2/\pm 45]_S$ laminate were examined to find transverse crack before failure. None of the specimens show any evidence of crack until the last loading step, which was in the range of 92 to 98% of the ultimate strength. A similar difference in off-axis layer failure between prediction and experiment was observed for the $[0_2/\pm 60]_S$ and $[0_2/\pm 75]_S$ laminates as shown in Table 2. The experimental result is the mean of five specimens. The theory also appears to underestimate the off-axis ply failure for the family of the $[0_2/\pm\theta]_S$ laminate. In spite of the numerous cracks extended to the entire off-axis layers in the $[0_2/\pm 60]_S$ and $[0_2/\pm 75]_S$ laminates, the experimentally-determined strengths are greater than those of prediction.

Experimentally-determined strength is significantly different between two families of the $[0/90/\pm\theta]_S$ and $[0/\pm\theta/90]_S$ laminates for $\theta \leq 45$ in spite of identical prediction as shown in Figure 9. For those laminates which did not show

TABLE 2
STRESS LEVEL AT THE FIRST-PLY FAILURE IN MPa

Laminate	Prediction	Experiment
$[0_2/\pm 60]_S$	465	544
$[0_2/\pm 75]_S$	390	471

any delamination until final failure, the experimental results are fairly well compared with the analytical results of the 0-degree layer. Experimentally-determined strength for the laminates experienced in delamination is markedly smaller than the predicted strength. Table 3 shows the stress level at onset of delamination determined by acoustic emission for seven to eight specimens of each laminate except for the $[0/\pm 10/90]_S$ laminate (two specimens).

TABLE 3
STRESS LEVEL AT ONSET OF DELAMINATION

Laminate	Stress, MPa
$[0/\pm 10/90]_S$	800
$[0/\pm 15/90]_S$	652
$[0/\pm 30/90]_S$	413
$[0/\pm 45/90]_S$	400

Figure 10 shows raw data of typical acoustic emission rate versus applied load for the $[0/\pm 15/90]_S$ and $[0/\pm 30/90]_S$ laminates. Sudden increase of acoustic emission signal is indicative of onset of delamination, and this signal remained practically at the same level until final failure. This is indicative of continuous propagation of delamination as a function of applied stress. A similar acoustic emission pattern was observed for the specimens of the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate. However, for the $[0/\pm 10/90]_S$ laminate, two types of typical acoustic emission patterns were observed as shown in Figure 11. The acoustic signal in Figure 11(a) shows strong indication of delamination upon failure, whereas Figure 11(b) does not show any indication of delamination. However, during examination of the free edges under step loading described previously, delamination was found in two specimens showing a similar acoustic emission pattern in Figure 11(b). The reason for failure of acoustic emission for detection of delamination in this case appears to be that the specimen fails upon delamination, which is limited to a very small area, as shown in Figure 4(a).

Although a number of transverse cracks were found in the respective off-axis ply in both families of the $[0/\pm \theta/90]_S$ and $[0/90/\pm \theta]_S$ laminates, especially for $\theta \geq 45$, there is no evidence of strength degradation due to these cracks, as there was in the case of $[0_2/\pm \theta]_S$.

CONCLUSIONS

Quadratic failure theory in conjunction with laminated plate theory has been applied to predict the in-plane tensile strength of multidirectional composite laminates. In analytical prediction, the ultimate failure of a laminate is assumed to occur upon the failure of the strongest ply in the laminate by ignoring the contribution of interlaminar stresses and transverse cracks preceded by final failure. The experimental result obtained from various types of laminates of T300/5208 graphite/epoxy was found to be in good agreement with

Figure 10. Typical Acoustic Emission Signals Indicating Onset of Delamination.

Figure 11. Typical Acoustic Emission Signals Indicating Onset of Delamination.

prediction with consistent exceptions. The exceptions are all the laminates show delamination at the free edges which substantially reduces the load-carrying capability. The experimental result indicates that the effect of transverse cracking on the strength appears to be insignificant for those laminates considered in this study. This approach has the advantage of simplicity and quickness in approximation of the in-plane tensile strength of multidirectional laminates.

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